

DONIESIENIA

Short notes

**The first record of *Hydaticus (Prodaticus) ponticus* SHARP, 1882
(Coleoptera, Dytiscidae) from Kazakhstan**

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Pierwsze stwierdzenie *Hydaticus (Prodaticus) ponticus* SHARP, 1882 (Coleoptera, Dytiscidae) w Kazachstanie

Hydaticus ponticus SHARP is a species from *fabricii*-group of the *Hydaticus* genus. It is a group of 10 species mainly from the Oriental region, with 5 species occurring also in the Palearctic region. This species has westernmost distribution from all of species from this group. It is recorded from eastern North Africa (Egypt and Libya), Saudi Arabia, Syria, Turkey, Iraq, Iran, Pakistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and northwestern India (WEWALKA G. 1979. *Koleopterologische Rundschau* 54: 119–139, BALKE M. & HENDRICH L. 1988. *Entomologische Zeitschrift* 98(1/2): 15–16, NILSSON A.N. & HÁJEK J. 2018. Catalogue of Palearctic Dytiscidae (Coleoptera). Internet version 2018-01-01 http://waterbeetles.eu/documents/PAL_CAT_Dytiscidae_2018.pdf). Now it has been also found in South Kazakhstan:

Kazakhstan, South Kazakhstan prov., 5 km W from Shardara (Шардара), N41°16'14" E67°3'02", 250 m a.s.l., 23-24.5.2016, 1♂, leg. Kucera, det. et coll. M. Przewoźny.

Until recently from Kazakhstan was only one species of *Hydaticus* known – *Hydaticus grammicus* (GERMAR, 1827), recently a second one was discovered – *Hydaticus pictus* (SHARP, 1882) (TEMRESHEV I.I. 2015. *Euroasian Entomological Journal* 14(6): 554). *Hydaticus ponticus* SHARP is a third species from this genus recorded from Kazakhstan. This is also the most northern locality of this species in its distribution, with a distant from the Tajikistan locality (Ura-Tyube: BALKE M. & HENDRICH L. 1988. *ibidem*) about 200 km north in a straight line.

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